

Description of Additional Supplementary Files

File Name: Supplementary Movie 1

Description: Interaction of water droplets with the surfaces of *A. macrorrhiza* (hydrophilic leaf) and *C. antiquorum* (superhydrophobic leaf).

File Name: Supplementary Movie 2

Description: Synchronization of the droplet dynamics on a leaf of *C. antiquorum* with the current signal produced on the same leaf.

File Name: Supplementary Movie 3

Description: Interaction of water droplets with the surface of *C. antiquorum* before and after modifying its surface waxes: pristine, after wax melting, after wax removal.

File Name: Supplementary Movie 4

Description: Interaction of water droplets with *H. helix*, *N. oleander*, *N. nucifera* and *T. majus*.